

A Study On Aadhar Privacy And Personal Security Issues In India

Dr. Hemant Kumar.S

Professor
CMS Business School
Jain University, #17, Sheshadri Road
Gandhi Nagar,Bangalore- 560009

Dr. Sahana Madan

Associate Professor
& CMS Business School
Jain University, #17, Sheshadri Road
Gandhi Nagar,Bangalore- 560009

Abstract

India's much tested biometric experiment aadhar has aroused a hot and most debated topic on data privacy and personal security issues in India. By interlocking the biometric card with the Intelligence grid, the colossal database can be shared with various other intelligence agencies, government departments and may also emerge has centralisation of power problem. So the primary diligence of this research is to understand the privacy concerns relating to the implementation of Aadhaar project. The study analysed the impact of aadhar on private and personal security of Indian citizens. In this research we examined the extent to which aadhar is essential for national security, foreign handling, centralisation of power problem, compromising citizens right to privacy, and bank misuse. The sample included 164 respondents in the age group of 18yrs to 65yrs and above. Random sampling method was used for data collection. The Aadhaar technology architecture does not seem to have been explicitly designed to have strong protections against such insider leaks and biometrics has the ability to create trusted identities, and also high degree of risk towards privacy. Research analysis suggests that firstly the legal framework should be more specific and strengthened, frequent policy updations as and when it arises. Aadhaar is a good example of Indian governments well intended biometric plan and novel idea to reduce bureaucracy and fraud, is now threatening the individual privacy of all its users and limiting the constitutional rights of Indian citizens.

Key words: *Aadhar, Privacy, Personal security, Implementation and Policies.*

1. Introduction

Aadhaar is a 12-digit ID number issued by the Indian government to each individual occupant of India, Jacobsen (2012) and Yadav, (2013). In 2001 a gathering of pastors headed by L.K.Advani presented its report in May and acknowledged proposal for an id card. Their report said the "multipurpose national personality card" undertaking would be begun soon Ramakumar, (2010). In September, Ministry of outer issues suggested that a required national character ought to be issued. In April 2010, the logo and the brand name Aadhaar was propelled by Nilekani.

In May, Nilekani said he would bolster an enactment to secure the information held by the UIDAI, Ramanathan, (2010). In July, UIDAI distributed a rundown 15 of organizations which were met all requirements to give preparing to staff to be engaged with the enrolment procedure. It likewise distributed a rundown of 220 offices which were met all requirements to partake in the enrolment procedure.

The Unique Identification Authority of India (UIDAI), which works under the Planning Commission of India, is in charge of overseeing Aadhaar numbers and Aadhaar ID cards. The Aadhaar venture was started as an endeavour towards having a solitary, one of a kind recognizable proof report or number that would catch every one of the subtle elements, including statistic and biometric data, of each occupant Indian person. At present there are a plenty of character reports in India including travel papers, lasting record numbers (PANs), driving licenses and apportion cards. The Aadhaar card/UID won't supplant these ID reports however can be utilized as the sole recognizable proof confirmation while applying for different things. It will likewise fill in as the reason for Know Your Customer (KYC) standards utilized by banks, money related foundations, telecom firms and different organizations that keep up client profiles. Aadhaar numbers will in the end fill in as the reason for a database with which burdened Indian occupants can get to administrations that have been denied to them because of absence of recognizable proof archives.

An occupant Indian can apply for the Aadhaar number and card by presenting the current verification of personality (visa, PAN card, driving permit, and so forth.) and confirmation of address (telephone/control charge, bank explanations, and so forth.) and by experiencing biometric profiling (fingerprints and iris examine) at any Aadhaar focus.

Reetika Khera (thewire Article, 2017) Privacy has been a key spotlight in the on-going discussion on Aadhaar. This is an extremely welcome advancement. Protection is being translated in various, similarly substantial, courses by various arrangements of individuals. In any case, the distinctions in understandings are not constantly clear to the individuals who take an interest in the discourses. For example, when PC researchers utilize the word protection, they watch out for it translate from a limited 'information security' point of view, while the legal advisors in the Supreme Court have been featuring the common freedoms edge to it. This has brought about gatherings talking past each other – the arrangements that the PC researchers propose, for example, (as more grounded benchmarks for information security, including encryption) are not agreeable to the individuals who feature the common freedoms parts of protection. Productive discussion on the issue requires a more detailed take a gander at the diverse measurements of security.

Specialists, nonetheless, trust that for unified databases the inquiry isn't whether it very well may be hacked, yet when. For example, Bruce Schneier, revealed to Pranav Dixit (July 2017), "When this database is hacked – and it will be – it will be on account of somebody breaks the PC security that ensures the PCs really utilizing the information."

A related worry that has been featured is that regardless of whether information are secure, with Aadhaar-empowered Payments System (AePS), the Aadhaar venture has made a weakness to character extortion, even data fraud. The thought behind AePS is, as Prime Minister Narendra Modi put it, 'Your thumbprint is your bank'. Unique mark impressions, in any case, can be effortlessly replicated. For example, as of late Hindustan Times announced that 200 understudies in Mumbai recreated their fingerprints on a generally utilized tar to fudge biometric participation. Simple gathering of biometrics attributes and freely accessible Aadhaar numbers increment the danger of managing an account misrepresentation. In the light of this developing budgetary innovation foundation which rides on Aadhaar and biometrics, the on-going 'Aadhaar holes' embarrassment (whereby Aadhaar quantities of lakhs

of individuals were shown on government gateways) is noteworthy. The developing AePS engineering opens the way to wholesale fraud. Indeed, even without information breaks, that is a disturbing rupture of protection.

2.Literature Review

Agar, (2005) and Whitley,(2010) Said "The possibility of a distinguishing proof plan initially picked up energy in the setting of the First World War. This prompted the making of a populace enlist as per the principal National Registration Bill". Thompson,(2008) A comparative sort of enlist was presented amid the Second World War however it was then allotted with an assortment of purposes like organizing national administration, national security and the organization of proportioning.

Solove (2006), Ahmed et al., (2005) contends that "Security is excessively entangled an idea, making it impossible to be come down to a solitary pith". Others call attention to that its social interpretation outside the West further confuses customary originations of protection, particularly around advancing innovations. Marwick and boyd, (2014); Nissenbaum,(2011)Paradigms of online security including notification and-assent, educated decision, and the production of access-control records via web-based networking media are altogether in view of individualistic originations of protection and underline security as an individual right.

Altman, (1977) Critics of individual jogged models contend that security hones are profoundly socially particular and logical. Marwick and boyd, (2014) To accomplish protection, people must have the capacity to both comprehend and impact the setting in which data is being translated, either "by co-developing the design of the frameworks" or "by implanting significance and setting into the substance itself".

Ramakumar, (2010) 'Illicit movement has accepted genuine extents. There ought to be mandatory enlistment of natives and non-subjects living in India. This will encourage arrangement of a national enlist of natives. All subjects ought to be given a Multi-reason National Identity Card (MNIC) and non-residents ought to be issued personality cards of an alternate shading and outline'. Since its source the UIDAI has guaranteed that Aadhaar will be a solitary evidence of character that could be utilized to look for profits by crosswise over open and private segment offices. Additionally it has likewise been asserted that UID would fill an assortment of needs: 'better focusing of government's advancement plans, administrative purposes (counting tax assessment and authorizing), security purposes, keeping money and budgetary area exercises, and so forth.

Protection as a "Right" in the Constitution

Supreme Court Statement (1994) prior to dissecting the protection issues around UID, it is imperative to inspect the hugeness of security in the Indian Constitutional custom. The Constitution of India does not unequivocally perceive the privilege to security but rather over and over its reality has been acknowledged through a few Supreme Court decisions. To expand this position, I might want to cite two or three judgements of the Supreme Court, the last mediator of the Constitution, from A.G. Noorani's review on protection distributed in the Frontline. He composes, 'In the Nakheeran case [R. Rajagopal versus State of Tamil Nadu

(1994) 6 SCC 632], the court stated: (Noorani, 2011) 'The privilege to protection is verifiable justified to life and ensured to the residents of this nation by Article 21. It is a 'right to be allowed to sit unbothered'. A native has a privilege to shield the security of himself, his family, marriage, reproduction, parenthood, kid bearing and instruction, among different issues'.

Black Money judgment (2010), Noorani, (2011) The judgment of the Supreme Court in the second case, Ram Jethmalani versus Union of India, is the latest one. The case is famously known as the Black Money case. In that, Justices P. Sathasivam and H. L. Gokhale watched: 'Appropriate to security is an indispensable piece of ideal to life. This is a treasured sacred esteem, and it is vital that individuals be permitted areas of flexibility that are free of open examination except if they act in an unlawful way.

Kashyap, (2001) The Supreme Court decisions referred to above clarifies that the privilege to protection is a certain piece of the Article 21 of the Constitution that expresses, "No individual will be denied of his life or individual freedom aside from as indicated by system set up by law". It implies that any infringement of the privilege to security must be considered as an encroachment of a crucial right.

A. P. Singh, the DDG, UIDAI says; 'Today there is no uncertainty about it. We have enlisted 200 million individuals which is the biggest database on the planet and the disappointment rate is under 0.5percent. He additionally includes that '...Because we take ten fingerprints, even one is sufficient to de-copy and if none of them are... the iris is sufficient to de-copy'. He likewise expresses that 'with the exception of 0.5 present we have possessed the capacity to de-copy everybody' and 'we are stating that 0.5 present additionally we will handle'

Ashok Pal Singh, the Deputy Director General (Admin), UIDAI, says:

'The moment the data is keyed in it is encrypted with the highest level of security, so we believe that it is not possible for that agency to extract that data even a second after it is encrypted. That is one. Secondly, there are definite conditions for the enrolment agency that for how long it can even keep the encrypted data package and they are not allowed to replicate it. So, the agency has absolutely no control over it.'

The Supreme Court of India in 1996 PUCL judgement clearly backed off from providing any prior judicial scrutiny in matters of data privacy and unlawful surveillance. Rather, it expressed that it is the focal government's part to outline laws and set out the procedural structure to control unlawful observation. Thus, the making of any institutional device lies in hands of Parliament. Be that as it may, Clause 33(1) says "divulgence of data, including character data or verification records, [can be] made in accordance with a request of a court."

Why might legal issue a request to the exposure of the UID data?

In 2014, the Bombay High Court suppressed and considered mistaken the judgment gone by the Goa High Court to give the CBI biometric information of all occupants selected in the Aadhaar program in the state to help tackle the group assault of a seven-year-old young lady. In spite of the fact that for this situation, the Bombay High Court had expelled the request, this proposed charge reflects how in coming occasions the legal can arrange the divulgence of biometric data for criminal examination or for reasons of national security.

By and large, this whole proposed charge mirrors the interlocking of reconnaissance systems and development of state forces to put its residents under observation for the sake of

administration. In spite of the fact that it was propelled to encourage productive conveyance of welfare administrations, it additionally enables the state to extend its surveilling space by bringing each person under its look. Post 26/11 Mumbai assault, India's insight assembling and activity systems were rethreaded by propelling NATGRID (National Intelligence Grid). It is a specialized interface or focal help focus, with an incorporated office, which plans to connect databases of 21 classes (e.g. travel, wage impose, driving licenses, financial balance subtle elements, migration records, phone and so forth). Notwithstanding that, it would be imparted to 11 focal organizations (eg. CBI, IB, R&AW, NIA and so on.). It is, basically, 'dataveillance' as it utilizes individual information frameworks in the examination and checking of the activities or correspondences of a person.

3. Statement Of The Problem

One of the recommendations of the Kargil Review Committee, that was established to review the state of national security within the wake of the Kargil intrusions. It was the difficulty of "Multi-purpose National Identity" cards to villagers living in conflict zones. It absolutely was afterward set to lead to increase this scheme to all or any voters, which became the origination purpose of Aadhaar. The most motive for this enlargement was to make sure the welfare of voters by comparatively easing their accessibility to numerous government schemes via one identification document. This junction rectifier to the institution of an avid establishment for rolling out the Aadhaar work referred to as the distinctive Identification Authority of Asian nation (UIDAI) on twenty eight Jan 2009. Nandan Nilekani, the Infosys co-founder was appointed because the chairman of UIDAI on twenty-three June 2009. After years of debates and deliberations, the Aadhaar act finally came into effect on 11th March 2016. The Aadhaar project created progress, at the same time the encircling debates saw a tectonic shift from frequent complaints concerning the show of incorrect knowledge or lack of clarity over its significance to hand tool problems with cyber security, fraud or knowledge breaches. so as to seek out if implication of aadhar card could be a breach on personal privacy? Hence this study on the privacy and security issues.

3.1 Scope Of The Study

The multiple, overlapping governing practices, with different capabilities and purposes, have empowered the Indian state with technologically-enabled surveillance. By interlocking the biometric card with the Intelligence Grid, the colossal database can be shared with various other intelligence agencies, government departments and may also emerge has centralisation of power problem, more importantly today digitalization of banking system is getting more technologically updated every day, hence linking of Aadhaar number to bank accounts will also face new challenges regards to breach on personal details and privacy issues bounded to it. Hence-fore keeping the above pointed issues and challenges regards UIDAI (Aadhar) breach on privacy, our study focuses on practical objectives stated below.

3.2 Research objectives

- To understand if aadhar card implementation is a breach on personal privacy
- To study if aadhar can help the government in future growth and potential development

- To study the willingness of citizens, acceptance for aadhar as their identity

3.3 Methodology

Primary data has been collected using a structured and focused questionnaire; which covered various dimensions of the research questions. While, secondary data has been collected from books, internet, literature and other relevant documents. Magazines, Journals, and Web resources, online libraries and websites are other sources. Here the sampling population is taken on based on convenience sampling, which impact on implication of aadhar card as a breach of privacy. Sample tests of 200 respondents were conducted Krejcie, R. V., & Morgan, D. W. 1970. Tools for data collection involved survey through questionnaires. Response was collected through hard copy.

Table 4.1 Indicating the Mean and Standard Deviation of the Aadhar privacy Dimensions

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
GENDER	150	1.29	.454
AGE	149	1.64	.780
EDUACTION	150	1.77	.942
Do you agree that government should be free to manipulate our personal data?	150	2.23	1.363
Do you think Aadhar help to prevent corruption?	150	3.02	1.353
Do you think Aadhar helps with public distribution system?	150	3.23	1.306
Do you think use of aadhar card in bank database is safe?	150	2.62	1.379
Do you think linking aadhar to bank will help the country to curb the black money?	150	3.09	1.409
Do you think Aadhar is essential for national security?	149	3.13	1.334
How safe is our individual information with the government?	149	2.36	1.175
Do you think corruption within the government will affect our individual data?	149	3.35	1.284
Do you think there is need for strong data piracy law?	150	3.97	1.129
Should contracts be issued to foreign rms to handle and manage our Aadhar data?	148	2.20	1.245
Do you think foreign firm handling our data is a national threat?	149	3.72	1.252
Valid N (listwise)	146		

The Data collection method involved is direct interview. A Likert scale 5-point is used in the set of responses for closed-ended questions. In each question, the respondents had to assess in

a five-point Likert scale (very low – very high) (Albaum, G. 1997). Hypothesis are made using the data and data analysis is being done using the statistical methods such as KMO measure of sampling adequacy and Bartlett’s Test of Sphericity has been conducted to identify the Communalities of the items used in the variable. ANOVA analysis, which is performed to study the Communication and service quality related specific to company as well as customers. Pearson Correlation analysis was conducted between Communication and Product and Service Quality to assess the relationship between the study variables.

Table 4.2 Indicating Sample Adequacy Test

KMO and Bartlett's Test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.649
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	401.213
	Df	105
	Sig.	.000

Table: 6 KMO Measure of Sampling Adequacy and Bartlett’s Test of Sphericity for Customer Survey From table 2 KMO value is 0.649 which is above .6 making the data sample suitable for the ‘Factor Analysis’. Also, the significance level (p) is .000 which is less than 0.05, making the factor analysis valid. As $p < 0.05$, we reject the null hypothesis (H0) and accept the alternate hypothesis (H1) that there may be statistically significant interrelationship between the variables

Table 4.3 Indicating Reliability of Data

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.631	14

TABLE 4.4 Representing the Correlation of Aadhar privacy Dimensions

Correlations				
		Centralisation of power problem	Bank misuse	Compromising Citizens right to privacy
Centralisation of power problem	Pearson Correlation	1	.462**	.273**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.001
	N	151	151	151
Bank misuse	Pearson Correlation	.462**	1	.308**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000
	N	151	151	151
Compromising Citizens right to privacy	Pearson Correlation	.273**	.308**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.001	.000	
	N	151	151	151

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

There is no significant relationship between various dimensions across on adhaar as an national security ID. It can be inferred that the Pearson Correlation is 0.462 which is statistically significant According to our survey out of 164 respondents, 27% have given that there is a chances to prevent corruption if aadhar card is implemented There is a 44% of the people have responded that the government should be free to manipulate our personal data. There are 29% of the people have agreed that the aadhar helps with public distribution system. Almost 58% of the people think aadhar is a distrust trap of greater regulation and lower economic growth. According to the response at only 28.9% people have agreed that the aadhar card in bank database is safe. There is 28.3% of the people have thought that linking aadhar to bank will help the country to curb the black money. There are 28.9% of the people have responded that the aadhar is essential for national security. There are 29%of the people have agreed that the aadhar card is our individual information with the government. Almost 31.5% of the random people have agreed that the corruption within the government will affect our individual data. There are 43% of the people have responded that there is need for strong data piracy law. There are 39% of the people have accepted that the contracts be issued to foreign rms to handle and manage our aadhar data. Almost 32.5% of the people have agreed that the foreign firm handling our data is a national threat

5. Implications And Suggestions

R.S. Sharma, chairman of TRAI (2017)(The Hindu), Since its inception, Aadhaar has been criticised as a project which violates privacy. India does not have a law on privacy. In fact, then chairman of UIDAI, Nandan Nilekani, wrote to the Prime Minister as early as in May 2010 suggesting that there was a need to have a data protection and privacy law. Therefore, the privacy bill should be the primary action towards the issues of breach in privacy.

- Similarly, people should be educated on the risk involved with ID thefts and fraud happening in digital world. IT laws should be strengthened and the liability should be bounded on companies handling data.
- Aadhar should focus and incorporate privacy by design itself, the technology and process towards collecting privet information should be protected parallely.
- As aadhar is an identity infrastructure collecting minimum set of data would be sufficient from residents, like name, age, address of resident and thumb impression.
- Prohibit the extensive use of aadhar number for every authentication or Proof of document, because aadhar is not a proof of identity document where, UIDAI doesn't even verify the address of the applicants. But still aadhar is accepted as proof of address in banking sector, telecom companies etc.
- Use of aadhar number should be only for required purpose like linking with direct subsidy and welfare schemes from central or state government example: Gas subsidy, BPL subsidy schemes etc.
- The errors of aadhar enrolment process should be looked upon, example the wrong identity photo or biometric authentication which are mismatching and also the end stage of reaching the aadhar cards to the respective holder is not effective.

- Aadhar as a welfare enhancing project should not turn into surveillance and data mining tool. Centralised and aadhar inter-linked database may lead to profiling and self-censorship, which endangers freedom of individuals.
- A report implied that several parties illegally tried to store the biometric data and conduct multiple transactions using the same fingerprint. So this would lead to misuse of aadhar, i.e The technology loopholes should be the utmost concern.

6. Conclusion

Thus, though there are serious privacy concerns at present, Firstly the legal framework should be more specific and strengthened, and also should make space for frequent and timely update on policies. The Aadhaar innovation engineering does not appear to have been expressly intended to have solid securities against such insider spills. We trust that successful security against insider spills essentially requires an outsider inspector under free authoritative control. With such an arrangement set up there are a few instruments from software engineering that can give sensible assurances to security and protection insurance, so that Aadhaar can be made safe from an innovation point of view with due-perseverance. Biometrics can make confided in personalities, and furthermore high level of hazard towards protection. So we trust Aadhaar venture requires educated and complete arrangement discusses, covering all points, to understand its full adequacy.

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